

Skill formation of female workers in the garment industry: The case of Bangladesh

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At a glance:

This policy brief outlines the participation of women in Bangladesh's skill-building processes within training institutions and factories, and highlights the challenges they encounter. Typically, women acquire formal qualifications from technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutes, along with informal on-the-job training in industrial settings. An analysis of their participation in skill development and their status in the labor market reveals a noticeable underrepresentation of women in formal and non-formal VET programs, particularly in the garment industry, at the technician and supervisor levels. Furthermore, women tend to be concentrated in basic skill positions within industrial establishments while being inadequately represented in middle- and high-level employment roles. This phenomenon is attributed to societal biases against women in the workplace. To enhance women's engagement in mid- and high-level industry positions, donor-funded initiatives must ensure their access to relevant courses. To overcome sociocultural barriers, it is imperative to integrate a gender and development component into all training programs with the agreement of stakeholders. Equally important is the provision of gender awareness training for educators, trainers, and institution managers to effectively identify and address gender-related issues and stereotypes. Collaborative efforts between NGOs and corporations have introduced non-formal training programs, encouraging young women to pursue mid-level roles in the garment sector, a strategy that merits wider adoption.

Introduction:

High-quality Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has been identified as a key mechanism for providing the labor market with skilled, productive, and competitive human resources (Haolader et al., 2017). Yet, gender disparity in TVET is a pervasive issue in most countries, including economically developed nations (ILO, 2020). This gender inequality is not solely a human rights concern but also acts as a hindrance to long-term economic progress for societies at large. In this context, promoting gender equality and fostering the empowerment of women and girls emerge as crucial components in accomplishing the objectives set forth by Sustainable Development Goal 5, which aims to "Attain gender equality and empower women and girls". This goal signifies not only a fundamental human right but also a cornerstone for constructing a sustainable global future (Nurhaeni and Kurniawan, 2018).

This policy brief encapsulates the outcomes focusing on inclusivity derived from the Skills for Industry research project. The insights are based on three primary data sources: official educational statistics, a survey involving 100 ready-made clothing companies, and interviews with 34 individuals representing authorities, training providers, and industry associations. The brief aims to shed light on the challenges faced by women in their engagement with training programs and the workplace.

In Bangladesh, TVET programs endeavor to enhance economic development by promoting employability

and inclusivity, especially for disadvantaged women (NSDA, 2020; ILO, 2012). However, an existing case study from the Skills for Industry project has demonstrated that while some companies offer informal on-the-job training for supervisors and external training for technicians (Shimu, 2021), these opportunities are disproportionately limited for women.

Findings:

1.1 Female participation in Informal TVET (in-firm)

Bangladesh has seen remarkable manufacturing sector growth, reaching 46,110 factories, including 3,000 large ones (Shah, 2022). In 2022, the workforce was 70.78 million, with about one-third of the workers, approximately 24.99 million, being women (BBS, 2023, p.89).

Over the past three decades, women’s participation in the labor market in Bangladesh has significantly increased, notably driven by the ready-made garment (RMG) industry. The RMG sector, employing 4 million workers, of which 58 percent are women (<https://bida.gov.bd/readymade-garments>), has played a vital role in enhancing female workforce engagement. Yet, despite growing school enrollment rates among women, 36.4 percent of female workers in the industry lack formal education, limiting them to unskilled, low-paying, and low-productivity roles, inhibiting their ascent to higher-level positions within professions (Raihan & Bidisha, 2018).

In line with other studies on the RMG industry in Bangladesh, the company survey from the Skills for Industry project indicates an increase in the number of female workers between 2012 and 2017 in different occupational levels from lower to higher. However, it also documents the fact that men still largely hold mid- to high-level positions. In the garment sector, there is a concentration of female workers in lower roles such as general workers (43%) and operators (48%), with fewer in middle to higher positions (supervisory, technical, or managerial).

Figure 1: Comparison of employees by gender and occupational levels in RMG in 2017

Source: Company survey data, 2018, Skills for Industry project.

In addition, case study data from the Skills for Industry project underscore a notable trend in the recruitment of female workers in specific roles, particularly helpers and operators directly associated with production. This pattern is influenced by societal perceptions of women as being meticulous and caring, aligning with the requirements of these positions. Human Resource (HR) managers emphasize that certain tasks demanding precision and attention to detail are often entrusted to female workers, as they tend to exhibit these qualities more reliably than male workers.

One of the Human Resource (HR) managers stated:

We have a significant number of female employees working in the finishing section. Some tasks require extra care, and we tend to prefer assigning them to female workers, as male workers may exhibit less attention to detail. (Int5_RMG_321_HM)

Typically, many female employees commence their careers as helpers and progress through them by working closely with operators and facilitated by informal on-the-job training. However, ascending to mid-level roles like those of supervisors or production managers remains uncommon due to various socioeconomic factors. Female workers,

often hailing from lower-income families with limited education, find it challenging to access informal training opportunities and defy societal norms which discourage late-night overtime work, which, in turn, hampers their advancement to mid-level positions. One of the HR managers explained:

Girls work more as helpers or operators and less as supervisors or electricians because of the overtime work in the garment industry. In most cases, regular production work continues after regular office hours. Sometimes, the supervisor and technicians have to stay until twelve at night, and so girls do not show interest in becoming a supervisor or an electrician.
(Int6_RMG_19_HM)

The workload within the garment industry significantly impacts workers, affecting gender-based responses negatively, as many of the female workers cease to participate in informal on-the-job higher-level training programs. Male workers participate in higher-level on-the-job training and tend to cope better with the demands of the job at hand, while female workers, constrained by family and societal roles, face barriers to progression. This leads to a disparity in informal skill development within the companies, influenced both by women avoiding higher-level training due to their dual household and professional work burden, as well as the reluctance on the part of the companies to recruit women for mid- and high-level roles.

1.2 Female participation in formal TVET

Despite the increasing participation of females in general education, female enrolment in TVET remains low in Bangladesh. Programs catering to the garment industry show minimal female representation, particularly in lower-level positions (BANBEIS, 2022; BTEB, 2022). In 2021, there were 172,796 admissions in national skills certificate (360-hours) courses, with female trainees constituting one-third of the total. A majority of these female trainees opted for courses in sewing machine operation and apparel manufacturing and

sewing, these being the entry/basic-level courses in the industry (BTEB, 2022). Bangladesh's formal education system also introduced vocational certificate courses alongside regular academic curricula for Secondary and Higher Secondary School Certificate (SSC and HSC) levels. In SSC (voc), two subjects are available: dressmaking and dyeing, and printing and finishing. Data from 2021, however, indicate low female participation in SSC (voc) examinations, with just a little over a quarter of the candidates being girls (figure 2). Only 12 percent female students participated in the HSC (voc) examination in the same year (figure 2).

The diploma degree is considered as the formal middle-level occupational degree in Bangladesh. Typically, garment companies prefer recruiting textile engineers, mechanical engineers, and electric engineers with diploma degrees, as these are deemed more valuable than other formal vocational education and training courses. However, in the year 2021, female participation in diploma courses was only 14 percent (BANBEIS, 2022; BTEB, 2022, figure 2).

On the other hand, the post-graduate diploma offered by five universities under Skills for Employment Investment Program (SEIP) includes management-level courses related to textile and RMG, particularly in two of the universities. Nevertheless, similar to the diploma degree, these management-level post-graduate diploma courses are predominantly attended by male students, reflecting the limited opportunities for females to secure employment in such positions within the industry.

Figure 2: Number of students who appeared in the TVET examination in 2021, by type of program and gender

Source: BTEB, 2022

Unlike participation in informal training, the reasons for lower levels of female participation in formal TVET courses are different and complicated. At the diploma level, one reason for lower female participation in the engineering department, with a focus on employability in the garment industry, is the discriminatory pay structures against females there. One of the instructors of a diploma institute said:

Despite completing higher education, only a few girls are offered managerial positions, and those who receive such offers decline due to the comparatively low salary. (Int 1- Bppl_DMPI)

This statement clearly shows that women are not willing to enroll in this diploma degree due to a persistent discriminatory pay structure at the company level. However, other reasons for rejecting still relatively high-paying managerial positions may be companies' relatively negative perception of female diploma graduates' skills (which goes against women's polytechnic institutes). In reply to this perception, the same respondent added:

If our girls aren't recruited, how can we identify the need for course improvement? Despite discrimination, some defy it, taking low-paid mid-level jobs, but this accounts for only up to 10%. (Int 1- Bppl_DMPI)

Due to a lack of job opportunities as well as a discriminatory payment structure, females are reluctant to participate in technical and supervisory courses, and the women's polytechnic institute has also stopped offering these courses to women. Consequently, these mid-level formal TVET training courses are becoming increasingly male-dominated, further attenuating female participation in the industry. Thus, formal TVET training programs are also failing to attract females to their mid- and higher-level training programs and position them in roles at the higher levels of the industry.

1.3 Female Participation in non-formal TVET

In Bangladesh, non-formal skill development is divided into public, private, NGO-based, and private (commercial) categories under the Skills for Employment Investment Program (SEIP). Within the SEIP project, a total of 782,104 individuals were enrolled from July, 2014 to November, 2023, with 31.47 percent (246,150) being women. Additionally, 474,849 individuals secured job placements, of which 34.6 percent (164,170) were women (<https://seip-fd.gov.bd/statistics/>). In this project, 209 courses are being offered through 574 institutes to develop lower-level occupational skills for industries. Here, women's participation in mid-level training courses is extremely limited, except for machine operator training for the RMG sector, where female participation is almost at 100 percent.

Public, private and NGO-based training institutes offer lower-level and mid-level management courses, approved by BTEB, which are occasionally modified in consultation with relevant companies. In principle, these programs prioritize the participation of economically disadvantaged women; in reality, however, females are predominantly enrolled in lower-level training courses and occupy lower-level positions in factories where no men are present. On the other hand, mid-level/technical positions (supervisor, machine maintenance, etc.) are mostly attended by men. Despite these facts, a few companies, in collaboration with NGOs, are making strides by recruiting women for such positions. The Skills Development Program (SDP) by BRAC provides outstanding non-formal training courses for current female employees, aiming to elevate them to supervisory roles through collaboration with companies. According to an SDP manager of BRAC:

We insist that the company selects existing operators who are capable of assuming supervisory positions and take selected female employees to our training center for 4 to 5 days, providing them with soft skills training to enhance their managerial capacity. Since the program's inception in 2021, we have promoted 380 females to supervisory positions. (Int3_bgp6_BRAC SDP)

No doubt, this is an exemplary initiative, providing numerous women with the opportunity to contribute to higher-level occupations in this sector. However, overall, women participation in higher-level on-the-job non-formal training courses is hindered by social attitudes towards women workers, their dual burdens, and other workplace-related issues that should be addressed rigorously.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This policy brief highlights the problems that women encounter during the skill-building processes in Bangladesh's technical and vocational education and training sector. Despite efforts to increase diversity, gender disparities continue to exist, especially in the garment sector. As we have seen, women are underrepresented in both formal and non-formal TVET programs, limiting their access to mid- and upper-level jobs.

Women continue to be concentrated in lower roles in the ready-made garment (RMG) industry, a significant contributor to female labor involvement, preventing their advancement to supervisory and managerial positions. Women are hesitant to engage in formal mid-level courses due to societal biases, family roles, and discriminatory wage structures, resulting in a male-dominated environment in these programs.

The following recommendations are aimed at addressing gender disparity in technical-vocational education to ensure women's equal access and opportunities in the labor market, all of which will contribute to building a more inclusive and economically progressive society:

1. Enhanced Access to Relevant Courses:

Donor-funded initiatives should prioritize ensuring women's access to relevant courses. This can be achieved through targeted support and scholarships to overcome financial barriers.

2. Integration of Gender and Development Component:

To overcome sociocultural barriers, it is imperative to integrate a gender and development component into all training programs. Stakeholders should play an active role in developing curricula and policies that promote gender equality.

3. Gender Awareness Training:

Gender awareness training is required for educators, trainers, and institution administrators. This will enable them to recognize and address gender-related issues and prejudices within their training environment, creating a more inclusive environment.

4. NGO-Corporate Collaborations:

Collaborative efforts between NGOs and corporations, such as the Skills Development Program (SDP) by BRAC, should be encouraged and expanded. Initiatives that recruit and train women for mid- and high-level roles in collaboration with companies can serve as models for broader industry adoption.

5. Address Discriminatory Pay Structures:

Efforts should be made to address discriminatory pay structures that discourage women from enrolling in higher-level diploma courses. Creating a fair and equal pay system will contribute to increased female participation in formal TVET programs.

6. Promotion of Non-Formal Training for Mid-Level Roles:

Non-formal training programs, especially machine operator training for the RMG sector, have shown promising results in achieving near-100percent female participation. The promotion and expansion of such programs can provide women with opportunities to develop mid-level occupational skills.

References

- Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information and Statistics [BANBEIS]. (2023). Bangladesh Educational Statistics 2022. Ministry of Education, Dhaka. <http://banbeis.portal.gov.bd> [20.01.2023].
- Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information and Statistics [BANBEIS]. (2022). Bangladesh educational statistics - 2021. Ministry of Education, Dhaka.
- Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics [BBS] (2023). Statistical Yearbook Bangladesh 2022. Ministry of Planning Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- BBS (2018). Report on Labour Force Survey (LFS) 2016-17.
- Bangladesh Technical and Education Board [BTEB]. (2022). SSC Vocational and Dakhil Vocational Routine 2022. Bangladesh Tech. Educ. Board.
- Bangladesh Technical and Education Board [BTEB]. (2022). Annual Report 2021-2022. Bangladesh Tech. Educ. Board.
- Haolader, F.A., Foyso, K.M., and Clement, C.K. (2017). Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Bangladesh – Systems, curricula, and transition pathways. Technical and Vocational Education and Training. 24. p. 201–227.
- ILO (2012). National Strategy for Promotion of Gender Equality in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) 2012. National Skills Development Council Secretariat, Government of Bangladesh in Collaboration with ILO TVET Reform Project
- International Labour Organization [ILO]. (2020). Understanding the Gender Composition and Experience of Ready-Made Garment (RMG) Workers in Bangladesh.
- National Skills Development Authority [NSDA] (2020)./ National Skills Development policy, 2020 [NSDP 2020]. Prime Minister's Office, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- Nurhaeni, I.D.A., and Kurniawan, Y. (2028). Gender-Mainstreaming in Technical and Vocational Education and Training. IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering.306 (1). doi:10.1088/1757-899X/306/1/012057
- Raihan, S. & Bidisha, S. H. (2018). Female employment stagnation in Bangladesh.
- Shah, J. (2022). Industries see growth from 313 factories to 46000. Prothomalo English. 27 March.
- Shimu, S. S. (2021). Relationships between VSD programs and industrial transformation in Bangladesh. University of Teacher Education Zurich & BRAC University, in Zurich (Switzerland) & Dhaka (Bangladesh) DOI: doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.5005055 (CC BY 4.0)
- <https://seip-fd.gov.bd/statistics/>

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